

REPRESENTATION OF KNOWLEDGE IN EXPERT SYSTEMS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11241746>

Abstract. *The article discusses knowledge assessment tools, as well as the goals and objectives of expert systems. Taking into account their positive and negative aspects and their practical use, it is concluded that in the future priority will be given to expert systems with a mixed, combined method of knowledge assessment.*

Keywords: *expert systems, program, application, database, neural network systems, interpretation, planning, forecasting.*

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются инструменты оценки знаний, а также цели и задачи экспертных систем. С учетом их положительных и отрицательных сторон и их практического использования делается вывод, что в будущем приоритет будет отдаваться экспертным системам со смешанным, комбинированным методом оценки знаний.*

Ключевые слова: *экспертных системах, программа, приложение, база данных, нейросетевые системы, интерпретация, планирование, прогнозирование.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada bilimlarni baholash vositalari, shuningdek, ekspert tizimlarining maqsad va vazifalari muhokama qilinadi. Ularning ijobiy va salbiy tomonlarini va ulardan amaliy foydalanishni hisobga olgan holda, kelgusida bilimlarni baholashning aralash, kombinatsiyalangan usuliga ega ekspert tizimlariga ustuvorlik berilishi hamda ulardan foydalanish haqida keltirilgan.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *ekspert tizimlari, dastur, ilova, ma’lumotlar bazasi, neyron tarmoq tizimlari, tahlil, prognozlash, rejalashtirish.*

Expert systems and artificial intelligence systems have the main difference from data processing systems in that they mainly use a symbolic method of representation, symbolic inference and heuristic search for a solution. Expert systems are designed to solve only complex practical problems. In terms of the quality and efficiency of the solution, expert systems should not be inferior to the decisions of a human expert. Expert systems solutions. can be explained to the user at a qualitative level, that is, they have transparency. The transparency of expert systems is ensured by their ability to reason about the results of their work and knowledge bases. An important property of expert systems is that they are capable of learning.

An artificial intelligence expert system that includes knowledge about a certain weakly structured and difficult to formalize narrow subject area and is capable of offering and explaining reasonable solutions to the user.

Knowledge base is a semantic model that describes a subject area and allows answering questions from this subject area, the answers to which are not explicitly present in the base. The knowledge base is the main component of intelligent and expert systems (Fig. 1).

In the future, the system considers various versions of the problem as theorems that need to be proven.

Neural network systems use learning methods aimed at modifying their own structure (network structure) and the weighting coefficients of connections between elements.

Evolutionary systems are built on the principles of genetic and evolutionary processes (algorithms), when the best “individuals”, most suitable for the solution, are selected from a set of candidates (population) obtained through crossing and mutation operations, according to an accepted criterion. They implement one of the effective approaches to solving multimodal (having several local extrema) optimization problems of large dimension. Evolutionary calculations do not guarantee the detection of the global extremum of the objective function (optimal solution) in a certain time, however, they allow one to find “good” solutions to very difficult problems [1, 43-p.].

- The main directions of research in the field of evolutionary computing are the following:
- evolutionary programming;
- evolutionary strategies;

Figure 1. Expert system structure

The key feature of expert systems is that it includes a knowledge base with a set of rules and allows, based on the facts provided by the user, to recognize a situation, make a diagnosis, formulate a solution or give a recommendation for choosing an action. The difference between expert systems and mathematical modeling systems is that it models the reasoning mechanism in relation to solving problems in a specific problem area [1, 11-p.].

Purpose of expert systems. Interpretation is the process of determining the meaning of data, the results of which must be consistent and correct.

Planning is a predetermined order, sequence of implementation of a program, work, or event.

Forecasting is a reasonable description of the sequence of events, with the possibility of discovering new factors.

Monitoring – continuous notification about the state of a system, application or process.

Design is the process of creating new information about an object or system (it is possible to exclude a professional from the design process).

Diagnostics is the process of recognizing a condition based on available factors

Training – user training, as well as self-training of the system, both at the stage of acquiring knowledge and during the operation of the ES (replenishment of the knowledge base (KB) of the ES with new output chains) [1, 12-p.].

The following classification of expert systems can be proposed:

- depending on the time scale (real time, pseudo real time, static);
- by type of knowledge (deterministic, uncertain).
- by source of knowledge (one, several).
- The following operating modes of the expert system are possible:
 - acquisition of knowledge;
 - consultations;
 - combined.

Expert systems really have wide applications in our lives. They save the time of real experts in a certain subject area. Knowledge representation models are an integral part of intelligent systems at any level. Therefore, I believe that every self-respecting IT specialist should have even superficial knowledge in these areas

REFERENCES

1. Борисов В.В., Бобряков А.В., Мисник А.Е. Экспертные системы. Учебное пособие по направлению «Информатика и вычислительная техника» – Смоленск: Универсум, 2021. – 110 с.
2. Федотов С.В. “Применение технологий искусственного интеллекта в кибербезопасности” – 2024. -С. 183-187
3. Сакулина Ю.В., Рожина И.В. Компьютерная графика как средство формирования профессиональных компетенций // Педагогическое образование в России. - 2012. - № 6. - С. 76 -80.
4. Морозова В.А., Паутов В.И. Представление знаний в экспертных системах учебное пособие / сост.— Екатеринбург: Изд-во Урал. ун-та, 2017. - С. 120.
5. Зарипов Н.Н. Использование иностранного опыта в обучении информатике и информационным технологиям в школе //Проблемы современного образования. – 2020. – №. 6. – С. 213-218.
6. Zaripov N.N., Hasanov B.N. Options for Working with Files in the Python Programming Language //Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 371-375.